

who is an author?

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Code
7701 5479

HOW TO Select a journal
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AVOID Predators
PHOTO CREDIT Geranimo

CRediT 14 Contributor Roles
PHOTO CREDIT Houcine Ncib

LICENCES: Types and uses
PHOTO CREDIT Karl Magnuson

NEW OA JOURNAL? Toolkit
PHOTO CREDIT Sara Cervera

Contributor Roles Taxonomy

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Credit is a high-level taxonomy, including 14 roles, that can be used to represent the roles typically played by contributors to research outputs. The roles describe each contributor's specific contribution to the scholarly output.

MORE INFO

- FOSTER
- Choose a license
- OSF licensing
- Open Source Initiative
- APACHE
- Creative commons

WHY?

1. Prevent your research from being used the way you did not intend
2. Reuse rights varies

LICENSE

CHECKLIST

- funder obligations
- Data repository
- Institutional policy
- Country or location

HOW TO SELECT?

It depends on different factors and needs

TYPES

1. Software & documentation
2. Non-Software Licenses

Tools previously developed by us

The online training material is designed for anyone interested in increasing their awareness of predatory academic practices. There is no cost to participate in this training materials. It is offered as an open educational resource by Sudanese National Academy of Sciences, University of Khartoum, University of Bahri and [IAP](#).

Pre-training questionnaire

Designed to determine your knowledge about predatory academic activities. It will take about 10 minutes to fill.

Is it a predatory conference?

Use this tool to help you decide whether it is a predatory conference or not. After submission, you can view your score.

Is it a predatory journal?

Use this tool to help you decide whether it is a predatory journal or not. After submission, you can view your score.

Criteria for Evaluating a Journal

- Scientific Rigor
- Editorial Quality
- Peer Review Process
- Ethics
- Editorial Board Members
- Journal Reputation/Business Model
- Author Rights and Copyright
- Indexing Status
- Impact Factor Scores????
- Journal Operations